

TIME AND SPACE CONSERVATIVE NONLINEAR HARMONIC METHOD

Hangkong Wu

School of Power and Energy
Northwestern Polytechnical University
Xi'an, Shaanxi, China

Dingxi Wang, Xiuquan Huang

Shaanxi Key Laboratory of Internal Aerodynamics in
Aero-engine
School of Power and Energy
Northwestern Polytechnical University
Xi'an, Shaanxi, China

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we propose a time and space conservative nonlinear harmonic method for analyzing temporal periodic unsteady flows. It starts from transferring an initial value problem to a boundary value problem. Then the time dimension is combined with the space dimension to form a time-space control volume over which the original differential unsteady equation is integrated. Same as the time spectral method (TSM) and the nonlinear frequency domain method (NLFD), truncated Fourier series are used to approximate unsteady flows. Different from the TSM and the NLFD method, both time and space are treated equally when forming a control volume leading to a time-space control volume. The derived discrete equation is similar to that of the NLFD method, and it is in a temporal integral form. Numerical results show that the method has higher accuracy and lower time cost in comparison with the NLFD method.

INTRODUCTION

The flow field within turbomachinery is inherently unsteady and largely periodic in time. To capture the unsteady flow field, there is a need to solve the unsteady Navier-Stokes equation [1, 2]. The time domain method [3-6] which performs time marching on a full annulus computational domain demands enormous memory and takes very long time. It is not suitable for routine design. In order to reduce time cost and save memory, a few frequency domain methods which make use of the temporal and spatial periodicity of the unsteady flow field have been proposed.

These frequency domain methods include the linear/nonlinear harmonic methods (LHM/NLHM) [7-11], the harmonic balance method or the time spectral method [12-16] and the nonlinear frequency domain method [17, 18]. Compared with the time domain dual time stepping method, these frequency domain methods can greatly reduce time cost and obtain a satisfactory solution if the

unsteady flow field can be efficiently represented using a very few limited number of harmonics. With the use of the phase shift boundary condition, the original full annulus or multiple passage computational domain can be reduced to one blade passage, significantly reducing the size of the computational domain leading to a great saving of analysis time cost.

Although all frequency domain methods use the truncated Fourier series to represent the conservative variables, these methods have their own different features. The LHM and NLHM have no aliasing problems, but it is difficult to be extended to an existing steady flow solver. Developing a new solver will increase the workload of programmers and limit their applications. The time spectral method and the NLFD method are easier to get into. The TSM solves the original unsteady equations at some carefully selected time instants directly. Therefore, the solution variables are same as those for a time domain solution. Fourier transformation is performed on the discrete flow solutions to obtain the temporal Fourier coefficients of the periodic unsteady flow which is then used to approximate the time derivative term in the form of time spectral source term. The NLFD method uses the discrete Fourier transformation to represent both the conservative variable and residual simultaneously. Different from the TSM, the solution variables are the temporal Fourier coefficients. Finally, the inverse discrete Fourier transform is used to transform the harmonic coefficients to the solution at all selected time instants.

For both the NLFD and the TSM, it can be considered that the original initial value problem is transferred to a boundary value problem. The size of the computational domain in the time direction is determined by the biggest period of unsteadiness with the periodic boundary condition being used for the lower and upper time boundaries. The select of time instants can be viewed as grid points in the time direction. Different from the spatial discretization which uses central or upwind schemes, spectral method is used in the time direction for a temporal discretization.

Though the NLFD method and the TSM treat the original initial value problem as a boundary value problem, the temporal and spatial discretization is still been treated differently when forming the discrete equations. Basically, a control volume excludes the time dimension and is based upon spatial dimension only. Referring to the method of space-time conservation element and solution element (SE/CE) [19, 20], we propose the time and space conservative nonlinear harmonic method. This method uses a time-space control volume concept when deriving the discrete equations. Different from the SE/CE method which needs to increase the number of variables, the TS-NHM uses the Fourier series to represent residual, the time integration of residual can be directly obtained. After time integration, we find that the governing equation of the TS-NHM is very similar to the NLFD method, and the former is in a temporal form. The advantages of the TS-NHM will be demonstrated in the following test cases.

This paper is arranged as follows: first, we make a brief introduction of the governing equation; then, we introduce the algorithm of the time and space conservative nonlinear harmonic method; finally, two cases including a quasi one dimensional case and a two dimensional cascade case are used to validate the effectiveness of the TS-NHM method.

NOMENCLATURE

q	conservative variable vector
\bar{q}	time-averaged variable
q_A, q_B	Fourier coefficients
r	residual
\bar{r}	time-averaged residual
r_A, r_B	Fourier coefficients of residual
u	velocity ($\frac{m}{s}$)
ρ, p	density ($\frac{kg}{m^3}$) and pressure (P_a)
E_t	internal energy ($\frac{J}{kg*m^3}$)
H	total enthalpy ($\frac{J}{kg*m^3}$)
Δx	grid size(m)
t_i	the i -th time instant (s)
ω	fundamental angular frequency
$\Delta \tau$	pseudo time step (s)
n	the number of harmonics
T	temperature (K)
T_t	time period (s)
F, G	flux in the x and y directions
D	Fourier transformation matrix
D^{-1}	inverse Fourier transformation matrix
κ	heat capacity ratio

TIME AND SPACE CONSERVATIVE NONLINEAR HARMONIC METHOD

To provide a simple illustration of the time and space conservative nonlinear harmonic method, we resort to the one dimensional unsteady Euler equation.

The one dimensional Euler equation in conservative form can be written as follows

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where

$$q = \begin{bmatrix} \rho \\ \rho u \\ \rho E_t \end{bmatrix}$$

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} \rho u \\ \rho u u + p \\ \rho u H \end{bmatrix}$$

p and H can be determined using the following formulas

$$p = (\kappa - 1) \left(\rho E_t - \frac{1}{2} \rho u^2 \right)$$

$$H = E_t + \frac{p}{\rho}$$

The time and space conservative nonlinear harmonic method starts from transferring an initial value problem to a boundary value problem under the circumstance of temporal periodic unsteady flows. This is achieved by first determining the size of the computational domain in the time direction which is the period corresponding to the fundamental frequency of unsteadiness. At the time boundaries, the periodic boundary condition will be applied. Hereafter we need to mesh the computational domain in the time direction in an analogy to gridding in space. In this paper, we discuss the situation where grid points are uniformly distributed over the time domain. Different from the spatial discretization where a center scheme with artificial dissipation is used, the spectral method is used to achieve the temporal discretization. Put simply, trigonometric functions will be fitted through the time instants to approximate the unsteady flows. This is equivalent to using truncated Fourier series to approximate temporal periodic unsteady flows.

Fig.1 Time-space control volumes

Figure 1 shows a time-space mesh where the horizontal axis denotes the spatial coordinate x and the vertical axis

denotes the temporal coordinate t . The spatial grid lines and temporal grid lines form time-space control volumes.

Integrating equation (1) over the time-space control volume of $(i, m+1/2)$, we can obtain

$$\iint \left(\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial x} \right) d\Omega = 0 \quad (2)$$

First, we deal with the first term in equation (2)

$$\begin{aligned} \iint \frac{\partial q}{\partial t} d\Omega &= \iint \frac{\partial q}{\partial t} dt dx \\ &= (q(t_{m+1}) - q(t_m)) \Delta x \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Then, we deal with the second term in equation (2)

$$\begin{aligned} \iint \frac{\partial F}{\partial x} d\Omega &= \iint \frac{\partial F}{\partial x} dx dt \\ &= \int_{t_m}^{t_{m+1}} \left(F(x_{i+\frac{1}{2}}) - F(x_{i-\frac{1}{2}}) \right) dt \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Let $r = F(x_{i+\frac{1}{2}}) - F(x_{i-\frac{1}{2}})$, and to get the time integration of r , we use truncated Fourier series to represent r .

$$r = \bar{r} + \sum_{i=1}^n (r_{A,i} \sin(\omega_i t) + r_{B,i} \cos(\omega_i t)) \quad (5)$$

Integrate equation (5) from t_m to t_{m+1} , and we can have

$$\begin{aligned} IR &= \int_{t_m}^{t_{m+1}} r dt \\ &= \int_{t_m}^{t_{m+1}} (\bar{r} + \sum_{i=1}^n (r_{A,i} \sin(\omega_i t) + r_{B,i} \cos(\omega_i t))) dt \\ &= \bar{r}(t_{m+1} - t_m) + \\ &\quad \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\omega_i} (-r_{A,i} \cos(\omega_i t_{m+1}) + r_{B,i} \sin(\omega_i t_{m+1})) - \\ &\quad \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\omega_i} (-r_{A,i} \cos(\omega_i t_m) + r_{B,i} \sin(\omega_i t_m)) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Substitute equation (6) and equation (3) into equation (2), and we can obtain

$$(q(t_{m+1}) - q(t_m)) \Delta x + IR = 0 \quad (7)$$

Let $Is = (q(t_{m+1}) - q(t_m)) \Delta x$ and add a pseudo-time derivative term to equation (7) for time marching

$$\frac{\Delta Iq}{\Delta \tau} \Delta x + Is + IR = 0 \quad (8)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} Iq &= \int_{t_m}^{t_{m+1}} q dt \\ &= \int_{t_m}^{t_{m+1}} (\bar{q} + \sum_{i=1}^n (q_{A,i} \sin(\omega_i t) + q_{B,i} \cos(\omega_i t))) dt \\ &= \bar{q}(t_{m+1} - t_m) + \\ &\quad \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\omega_i} (-q_{A,i} \cos(\omega_i t_{m+1}) + q_{B,i} \sin(\omega_i t_{m+1})) - \\ &\quad \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\omega_i} (-q_{A,i} \cos(\omega_i t_m) + q_{B,i} \sin(\omega_i t_m)) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Equation (8) is the governing equation in the temporal integral form over the time-space control volume $(i, m+1/2)$.

From equation (6) and equation (9), we find that there are $2n+1$ unknowns, therefore, $2n+1$ equations are needed. For TS-NHM, to have $2n+1$ equations, we need $2n+1$ control volumes in the time direction, thus we need $2n+2$ time instants or grid points in the time direction. These $2n+2$ time instants are usually uniformly distributed for one fundamental frequency case. For the case with multiple

fundamental frequencies, the almost periodic Fourier transformation (APFT) [21] method is used for the selection of the time instants. In this paper, we only take into consideration of the one fundamental frequency case. These $2n+2$ time instants can be expressed like this

$$t_m = \frac{m}{2n+1} T_t \quad (m = 1, 2, \dots, 2n+2) \quad (10)$$

where

$$t_{2n+2} = t_1 + T_t$$

According to the periodicity, we can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} r(t_{2n+2}) &= r(t_1 + T_t) = r(t_1) \\ q(t_{2n+2}) &= q(t_1 + T_t) = q(t_1) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Rewrite equation (6) and equation (9) in matrix form

$$IR = MR^* = MD^{-1}R \quad (12)$$

$$Iq = MQ^* = MD^{-1}Q \quad (13)$$

R^* and Q^* are the Fourier coefficients of R and Q . They are given as follows

$$\begin{aligned} R^* &= \begin{bmatrix} \bar{r} \\ r_{A,1} \\ r_{B,1} \\ \vdots \\ r_{B,n} \end{bmatrix}, \quad R = \begin{bmatrix} r(t_1) \\ r(t_2) \\ \vdots \\ r(t_{2n+1}) \end{bmatrix} \\ Q^* &= \begin{bmatrix} \bar{q} \\ q_{A,1} \\ q_{B,1} \\ \vdots \\ q_{B,n} \end{bmatrix}, \quad Q = \begin{bmatrix} q(t_1) \\ q(t_2) \\ \vdots \\ q(t_{2n+1}) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

D^{-1} is the inverse matrix of D . Matrices D and M are given in the following

$$\begin{aligned} D &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \sin(\omega_1 t_1) & \cos(\omega_1 t_1) & \cdots & \cos(\omega_n t_1) \\ 1 & \sin(\omega_1 t_2) & \cos(\omega_1 t_2) & \cdots & \cos(\omega_n t_2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & \sin(\omega_1 t_{2n+1}) & \cos(\omega_1 t_{2n+1}) & \cdots & \cos(\omega_n t_{2n+1}) \end{bmatrix} \\ M &= \begin{bmatrix} \Delta t_1 & -\frac{1}{\omega_1} (\cos(\omega_1 t_2) - \cos(\omega_1 t_1)) & \cdots & \frac{1}{\omega_n} (\sin(\omega_n t_2) - \sin(\omega_n t_1)) \\ \Delta t_2 & -\frac{1}{\omega_1} (\cos(\omega_1 t_3) - \cos(\omega_1 t_2)) & \cdots & \frac{1}{\omega_n} (\sin(\omega_n t_3) - \sin(\omega_n t_2)) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \Delta t_{2n+1} & -\frac{1}{\omega_1} (\cos(\omega_1 t_1) - \cos(\omega_1 t_{2n+1})) & \cdots & \frac{1}{\omega_n} (\sin(\omega_n t_1) - \sin(\omega_n t_{2n+1})) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\Delta t_i = t_{i+1} - t_i \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, 2n+1)$$

After the calculation of the integral variables, the following formula is used to obtain the solution at selected time instants

$$Q = (MD^{-1})^{-1} Iq \quad (15)$$

The dataflow diagram of the TS-NHM is shown in Figure 1. At the beginning of the iteration, an initial guess of conservative variables at all selected instants $q(t)$ is given. Using equation (13), we can obtain integral variables Iq for each time-space control volume. At each time instant, we can also compute the residual $R(q)$. Using equation (12), $R(q)$ is transformed to the temporal integral variable IR . We calculate the overall residual by adding the source term Is to IR . This overall residual is used to compute the new integral variable Iq which is then used to obtain the new approximate conservative variable q . This completes one cycle of the dataflow.

To make a comparison between the NLFD method and the TS-NHM, the time marching scheme of the NLFD method is shown as follows

$$\frac{\Delta \bar{q}}{\Delta \tau} \Delta v = \bar{r} \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{\Delta q_{A,i}}{\Delta \tau} \Delta v - \omega_i q_{B,i} \Delta x = r_{A,i} \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{\Delta q_{B,i}}{\Delta \tau} \Delta v + \omega_i q_{A,i} \Delta x = r_{B,i} \quad (18)$$

Equation (16) is the time-averaged equation. Equation (17) and (18) are the perturbation equations. The complete dataflow diagram of the NLFD method is shown in Figure 2. Similar to the TS-NHM, an initial guess of $q(t)$ is given first. Then we use a discrete Fourier transform to transform $q(t)$ to the Fourier coefficients q^* . At each time instant, the residual $R(q)$ can be computed, and then a discrete Fourier transform is performed to transform $R(q)$ to the Fourier coefficients $R^*(q)$. Adding the source term s to R , we can obtain the overall residual. The overall residual is used to compute the new Fourier coefficients q^* . Using an inverse discrete Fourier transform, we transform it back to the new approximate $q(t)$.

Fig.1 The dataflow diagram of the TS-NHM(k represents the k-th iteration)

Fig.2 The dataflow diagram of the NLFD method

From the above dataflows, it can be found that for the NLFD method, its solution variables are the temporal Fourier coefficients. However, for the TS-NHM, its solution variables are the temporal integral variables. Because of the difference of the source terms, the time cost of the two methods will also be different. For the TS-NHM, the time cost of the source term calculation is proportional to $(2n+1)$ (n represents the number of harmonics) at each grid point. However, for the NLFD method, the time cost of the source term calculation is proportional to $4n$. Therefore, the TS-NHM will save time cost in comparison with the NLFD method.

CASE1: QUASI ONE DIMENSIONAL LAVAL NOZZLE CASE

Fig.3 The mesh of the quasi one dimensional nozzle case

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the TS-NHM, two cases are used. The first case is the quasi one dimensional Laval nozzle case. The mesh is shown in Figure 3 and the grid points are uniformly distributed along the flow direction. The height distribution is shown as follows

$$h(x) = ax^2 + h_0$$

x is the grid position, and it ranges from -0.2 to 0.2 . a and h_0 are constant. In our test case, we set them to 0.5 and 0.01 respectively.

The boundary conditions for this case are set as follows: at the inlet, the subsonic inlet boundary condition is applied (total temperature of $300K$ and total pressure of $121325Pa$); at the exit, the subsonic outlet boundary condition (static pressure of $101325Pa$) is used.

Fig.4 The comparison of static pressure along the flow direction

Before we do unsteady calculation, we use the analytic solution to validate the steady flow solver. It can be seen from Figure 4 that there is good agreement between the analytic solution and the numerical solution.

We give back pressure perturbation to realize unsteady calculation. The perturbation function is shown as follows

$$p = \bar{p} + p_A \cos(2\pi ft) \quad (19)$$

\bar{p} represents the time-averaged back pressure and p_A is the perturbation amplitude of back pressure. f is the fundamental frequency. Their values are given like this

$$\bar{p} = 101325Pa, p_A = 0.07\bar{p}, f = 5000Hz \quad (20)$$

Fig.5 The spectral analysis by averaging the harmonic amplitudes in the whole flow field.

First, we did the unsteady flow analysis using the time domain method to obtain the unsteady flow field. Then, the spectral analysis shown in Figure 5 is performed in the whole flow field to determine how many harmonics can be retained in a harmonic analysis. It can be seen from Table 1 that with the increase of the number of harmonics, more internal energy will be retained. To retain over 98% of internal energy, there is a need to use 9 harmonics or more to analyse the unsteady flow field. More harmonics will greatly increase the CPU time and memory. To make a compromise, 9 harmonics will be used in the following part.

Tab.1 The internal energy retained in a harmonic analysis for different number of harmonics

The number of harmonics	Internal energy (%)
1	48.3
3	71.8
5	87.2
7	95.6
9	98.2
11	99.1

Figure 6 and 7 show the distribution of the time-averaged value and the first harmonic amplitude of internal energy along the flow direction. The time domain solution is used as the reference. From these two figures, we find that the solution of the TS-NHM agrees well with the time domain solution. To quantitatively compare the difference between the NLFD method and the TS-NHM, we define a dimensionless parameter named solution error. Its formula is given as follows

$$\epsilon = \lg_{10} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\sum_i (q - q_{ref})^2}{\sum_i q_{ref}}} \right)$$

i represents the number of grid points. q_{ref} is the time domain solution which is used as the reference. The solution error (ϵ) is presented in Figure 8. From this figure, we

find that the solution error will gradually decrease for both the NLFD method and the TS-NHM when more harmonics are used. At the same time, when using the same harmonics, the TS-NHM has lower solution error than the NLFD method, that is, the TS-NHM has higher solution accuracy.

Figure 9 makes a comparison in CPU time required for convergence between the TS-NHM and the NLFD method. It can be seen from this figure that the TS-NHM is more economic in CPU time than the NLFD method. The TS-NHM can save about 60% of time cost.

Fig.6 The distribution of time-averaged internal energy along the flow direction (rho_e represents the internal energy)

Fig.7 The distribution of the first harmonic amplitudes of internal energy

Fig.8 The solution error against number of harmonics for TS-NHM and NLFD method

Fig.9 The residual against time cost for TS-NHM and NLFD method

CASE2: TWO DIMENSIONAL INVISCID CASCADE CASE

The mesh and airfoil of the two dimensional cascade case is shown in Figure 10. At the streamwise direction, there are 113 grid points in total with 65 grid points on the blade surface. At the pitchwise direction, there are 33 uniformly distributed grid points. The boundary condition is set as follows: at the inlet, the subsonic inlet boundary condition is applied (total pressure is 111325Pa, flow angle is 37degrees and total temperature is 288.15K) and at the outlet, the subsonic outlet boundary condition (static pressure is 101325Pa) is used. On the blade surface, the slip wall boundary condition is applied. At the geometric periodic boundary, the periodic boundary condition is applied.

Fig.10 The mesh and airfoil of the two dimensional cascade case

Similar to the quasi one dimensional nozzle case, we give back pressure perturbation to realize unsteady calculation. The perturbation function is given as follows

$$p_b = \bar{p} + p_A \cos(2\pi ft) \quad (21)$$

where

$$\bar{p} = 101325Pa, p_A = 0.05\bar{p}, f = 2000Hz \quad (22)$$

Fig.11 The spectral analysis by averaging the pressure harmonic amplitudes on the upper and lower blade surfaces (two dimensional cascade case)

Tab.2 The pressure retained in a harmonic analysis with different number of harmonics (two dimensional cascade case)

The number of harmonics	Pressure(%)
1	96.9
2	99.2
3	99.5
4	99.6

According to the result of spectral analysis shown in Figure 11 and Table 2, it can be found that with the increase of the number of harmonics, more pressure will be retained in a harmonic analysis. To retain 99.6% of pressure, four harmonics will be used in the following part to analyse the unsteady flow field.

Fig.12 The comparison of the residual against time cost for different methods (two dimensional cascade case)

Fig.14 The distribution of the first harmonic amplitude of pressure on the blade surfaces for different methods(two dimensional cascade case)

Fig.13 The distribution of the time-averaged pressure on the blade surfaces for different methods (two dimensional cascade case)

Fig.15 The solution error against number of harmonics for TS-NHM and NLFD method (two dimensional cascade case)

Figure 12 makes a comparison in CPU time between the TS-NHM and NLFD method. It can be seen that the NLFD method consumes more CPU time than the TS-NHM. In comparison with the NLFD method, the TS-NHM method can save about 15% of CPU time. Figure 13 and 14 show the distribution of the time-averaged value and the first harmonic amplitude of pressure on the blade surface. There is good agreement between the TS-NHM solution and the time domain solution when the number of harmonics is set to four. To distinguish the difference of the NLFD method, the solution error (ϵ) is used again. In spite that with the increase of the harmonics, the solution error will decrease for both the NLFD method and the TS-NHM shown in Figure 15, the TS-NHM has lower solution error (higher solution accuracy) than the NLFD method when the number of harmonics is set to the same value.

CONCLUSIONS

A time and space conservative nonlinear harmonic method has been proposed. The method is based upon the integral form of the original unsteady equation over a time-space control volume which is formed by transferring the original initial value problem to a boundary value problem. Two numerical cases were used to investigate the proposed method. According to the quasi one dimensional Laval nozzle case and the two dimensional cascade case, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- (1) In comparison with the NLFD method, the TS-NHM is more economic in CPU time;
- (2) With the increase of the number of harmonics, the solution accuracy of TS-NHM will be improved;

- (3) When using the same number of harmonics, the TS-NHM has higher solution accuracy than the NLFD method.

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